

Primary angiitis central nervous system for young adult with retinitis: Case Report

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Abstract

Primary angiitis central nervous system with multiple cerebral cortex and retinal involvement, it is very rare cases, in the literature, PACNS associated with retinal involvement,

In our case is the case report for difficult diagnostic dilemma, with multiple clinical medical trail, also highlighted the accurate diagnostic of PACNS by STB (stereotaxic Biopsy) histopathological and management.

Keywords: Primary angiitis central nervous system; Retinal; Stereotaxic Biopsy; Histopathological

1. Introduction

Primary angiitis of the central nervous system (PACNS) is a rare and severe disease. It was first described by Harbitz in 1922 as an unknown form of angiitis in the CNS. (1) Isolated vacuities of the central nervous system, primary CNS vasculitis, and isolated angiitis of the CNS are common synonyms for the disease.

PACNS mainly affects younger stroke patients lacking cerebrovascular risk factors. (2) Approximately 3–5% of cerebrovascular events in patients aged <50 years are caused by primary CNS vasculitis (3) The mean age of the initial manifestation of adult PACNS is at the end of the fourth decade (3) In retrospective analyses a similar frequency in male and female patients has been shown (4)

Clinical features at diagnosis are highly variable and nonspecific; classic or pathognomonic clinical symptoms are lacking. Major symptoms of cerebral vasculitis are headache (60%), altered cognition (50%) and focal neurologic deficits (e.g. hemiparesis, ataxia, aphasia, dysarthria and visual disturbances) (2) Furthermore seizures and encephalopathy have been reported. In general, the onset of disease is insidious and slowly progressive, but an acute beginning of symptoms can occur (2) Marked constitutional symptoms such as fever, weight loss and night sweats are less frequent and can be indicative of systemic vasculitis (5)

An extremely low annual incidence of 2.4 cases per million patient/years is reported (4). It was considered a distinct clinical entity in 1959 by Cravioto and Feigin. (6) (The diagnosis remains a challenge, since there are no universally accepted diagnostic criteria and imaging findings may not be specific. Different types of clinical presentation have been described, which makes it even more difficult to identify. Unlike systemic vasculitis, this entity lacks positive autoantibodies.

In our case we report PACNS young adult with retinitis, which is successful diagnosis stereotaxic biopsy and treated corticosteroid and respond well.

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2. Case Report

A 22 year old male patient admitted in the department of the neurosurgery at Avicenna hospital in Rabat for head age associated with ,convulsion partial at left side then generalized tonic clonic seizure ,dysarthria, and visual disturbance for short slightness, for 2 years, no vomiting ,there is no history of trauma ,also he develop hemiparesis after couple of month , and admitted at department of the neurology , he had past history of the vasculopathic retinitis, at 2020 treated by ophthalmologist , after the symptoms worsening and also had history of the treatment for tuberculosis ,and epileptic drugs, at department of the neurology , there is no positive family history , Physically patient weight loss up to 10 kg and no jaundice, cyanosis, pale, he is conscious, Gcs 15/15,well oriented and alert ,hemodynamically and respiratory are stable ,pupil equal and reactive , walking normal, there is facial palsy grade 2 on the left hemi facial, also Motoric dysarthria , the power is 4/5 at the left side upper and lower limbs , sensory are intact , and coordination normal .

All routine blood work up was normal and inflammatory markers ANA/ANCA all negative, tuberculosis test negative.

For radiological assessment; - done MRI cerebral,

Figure 1 Multiple lesion hyper intense on the cerebral surrounding small edema T1 injected

Finger 2 Flair there massive edema perilesional at right front- parietal

Finger 3 Ophthalmological test, there right side retinal vacuities

Finger 4 Angiography cerebral there is minor lacunar vacuities

Then patient had stereotaxic biopsy (STB) at right side of the cerebral after the histopathological examination confirm lymphocytic inflammatory vasculitis, with gliosis reaction (PACNS) primary angiitis central nerve system .then start treatment for the corticosteroid, immediately after diagnosis.

Finger 5 Post STB control no complication

3. Discussion

PACNS is an entity poorly understood and significant challenges remain for diagnosis and treatment [6]. However, there has been an increased recognition with the diagnostic criteria proposed by Calabrese and Mallek and the number of reported cases have risen substantially. The general advances in diagnosis of these neurological disorders have led to an aggressive diagnostic approach and enriched clinical and pathological descriptions [5,7].

Histologically, the inflammatory process commonly is lymphocytic and affects the medium-sized and small arteries and arterioles of the meninges and cortex of the brain and only rarely the veins and venules. The classic findings of segmental granulomatous vasculitis with multinucleated giant cells occur in less than 50% of patients. Necrotizing vasculitis occurs in 25% of patients. The presence of intimal fibrosis usually signifies healed lesions [8].

The clinical, imaging, and angiography spectra can be very broad. The median age of onset is 50 years, but may affect patients of all ages. The neurological manifestations are diverse, ranging from hyperacute to chronic and insidious. Generally, PACNS consist of headache, altered cognition, focal weakness, or stroke occurring in 30–50% of patients, usually affecting many different vessels [7].

Different patterns and outcomes of the disease have been described, like fulminant-disease onset, spinal involvement [9], prominent leptomeningeal enhancement, and negative cerebral angiography, suggesting that medium-sized vessels are affected. CSF examination reveals evidence for aseptic meningitis in over 90% of patients [10]. Another presentation was described by Molloy et al. [8] characterized by a mass-lesion, making the pathological confirmation essential for diagnosis. Sometimes aggressive immune suppressive treatment could obviate the need for excision [11] At last; there is a group of vasculitis that is characterized by abnormal cerebral angiography and CSF examination but usually a normal brain in the biopsy.

The most important differential diagnosis is the systemic vasculitis, which is characterized by the presence of constitutional symptoms and serological markers indicating systemic inflammation [12]. The hallmark of the PACNS is that inflammatory process is limited to the CNS. Diseases that can mimic PACNS are the reversible cerebral vasoconstriction syndrome, premature intracranial atherosclerosis, fibromuscular dysplasia, moyamoya disease, brain neoplasms, genetic conditions (e.g., CADASIL), posterior reversible encephalopathy syndrome (PRES), chronic hypertension (microvascular cerebral ischemia), demyelinating diseases, and others with multifocal cerebral thromboembolism. It is important to notice that infections (i.e., *Varicella zoster* virus, HIV, and hepatitis C virus) have been associated with cerebral angiographic abnormalities and should be excluded with serological tests [13, 14]. Tuberculosis is another important mimic of PACNS.

No single laboratory test has sufficient sensitivity or specificity to establish the diagnosis, and high clinical suspicion is necessary. Brain biopsy is required to confirm the diagnosis and exclude other causes. Based on published studies, the estimated sensitivity of cerebral angiography for detection of vasculitis is between 27% and 90% and for brain biopsy between 36% and 83% [5, 7]. MRI is the main neuroradiographical modality for the workup of patients with suspected PACNS, and generally, the combination of normal findings on MRI and normal CSF analysis has a high negative predictive value for the diagnosis of PACNS [11].

A common pitfall in the workup diagnosis is to start immunosuppressive treatment without establishment of diagnosis or exclusion of other diseases. Unfortunately, no randomized studies of PACNS have been done, and thus all information on treatment is based on retrospective observational data and clinical experience. The efficacy of most immunosuppressive agents such as azathioprine, methotrexate, and rituximab that are used in systemic vasculitis is still unknown or remains elusive in PACNS [12]. The vast majority of case series suggest a high degree of good outcomes when patients are treated with glucocorticoids or glucocorticoids and cyclophosphamide. However, there are some reports using a therapy combining mycophenolate mofetil and steroids allowing control of the disease with disappearance of the neurological abnormalities, restoration of normal daily activities and dramatic improvement in brain MRI abnormalities [14].

The majority of PANCS reports are from Europe and North America [15]. In Latin America there are no reports of PACNS, and we do not really know the incidence and prevalence of this entity in Colombia. Takayasu arteritis was the most frequently reported form of primary vasculitis overall, from Colombia [16], Brazil, and Mexico ,Even though we think there is some experience with PACNS in Latin America, it has not been published.

In our case report presenting the Importantly to know the clinical heterogeneous presentation of this condition when we handled this group of patients, even the possibility that it has of simulate psychiatric or malignant disorders like from described patients. The high clinical suspicion and appropriate diagnostic approach focused on problems, taking into account unusual entities like this, and it will make one accurate diagnostic and therapeutic approach. We hope that with this case report the medical community is encouraged to report more cases and thus in this way achieve a unanimous concept in respect to the management, diagnostic and therapy of this entity which has a high mortality rate.

4. Conclusion

Primary angiitis central nervous system, which is involved cerebral cortex and retinal most be considers very important differential diagnosis for multiple focal lesion of cerebral, which is mimic to metastatic tumors, infection (tuberculosis), and other inflammatory central nervous system, although extremely rare cases, its clinical important to diagnosis and assessment different clinical presentation, and immediately intervention will improve the outcome of the patient.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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